

Safety Analysis of SMR with PAssive Mitigation strategies - Severe Accident

Deliverable 2.3 Analyses of the employment of ATFs in iPWR scenario analyses Version 0

Disclaimer

Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

While this document has been prepared with care, the authors and their employers provide no warranty concerning the content and shall not be liable for any direct, incidental or consequential damages that may result from the use of the information or the data contained in it. Reproduction is authorised provided the material is unabridged and the source is acknowledged.

Document type	Deliverable
Document number	Version 0
Document title	Analyses of the employment of ATFs in iPWR scenario analyses
Authors	M. E. Cazado (KIT)
Contributing Partners	ENEA: P. Maccari, F. Mascari KIT: M. E. Cazado, F. Gabrielli, V. H. Sánchez-Espinoza LEI: M. Valincius, A. Kaliatka RUB: J. Krieger, G.T. Stahlberg, M. K. Koch UNIROMA1: M. Principato, G. Marta, F. Giannetti VTT: T. Sevón
Release date	22/06/2026
Contributing partners	KIT
Dissemination level	OPEN

Version	Short description	Main authors	Coordinator
0	Draft	M. E. Cazado (KIT) Date, 25.07.2025	F. Mascari (ENEA) Date, 25.07.2025
1	Final	M. E. Cazado (KIT) Date, 22.06.2026	F. Mascari (ENEA) Date, 22.06.2026

Abstract

The HORIZON-EURATOM SASPAM-SA project, which was initiated in 2022 and is being coordinated by ENEA (Italy), is addressing a critical knowledge gap in the analysis of Severe Accidents (SAs) and Emergency Planning Zone (EPZs) for Integral Pressurised Water Reactors (iPWRs). The project aims to transfer the expertise developed for large light water reactors (LWRs) for use with iPWRs, thereby aligning with European licensing requirements. A key objective is to evaluate the predictive capabilities of state-of-the-art integral safety analysis codes — both European and non-European — in simulating postulated SA scenarios in two generic iPWR designs that are representative of leading concepts in the European market.

As part of the Work Package 2 (WP2-SCENARIO), the SASPAM-SA partners conducted an extensive study to assess the applicability and performance of the leading integral codes for modelling SA phenomena in two selected generic iPWR designs. This report presents the evaluation of Design-1 and Design-2 concepts with the codes ASTEC, MELCOR and AC², focusing on the behaviour of ATFs, specifically FeCrAl cladding, under SA conditions. Simulations were conducted by KIT, RUB-PSS, VTT, ENEA, LEI and UNIROMA1. Based on current knowledge and at the start of the accident, the main objective was to evaluate the influence of FeCrAl cladding on accident progression compared to conventional Zircaloy cladding, with focus on the hydrogen generation. This report provides a comparative evaluation of iPWR designs, discusses the modelling strategies employed for ATFs in the different codes and outlines the key findings and limitations of the simulations.

Table of contents

Disclaimer	2
Abstract	3
Table of contents	4
1 Introduction	5
2 Generic iPWR Design-1 and Design-2 description	6
3 ATF Modelling Approaches	8
3.1 ATF Modelling Approach for ASTEC	9
3.2 ATF Modelling Approach for AC ²	10
3.3 ATF Modelling Approach for MELCOR	10
4 Postulated accident scenarios	12
4.1 Generic iPWR Design-1	12
4.2 Generic iPWR Design-2	12
5 iPWR Design-1: Summary of the results of the postulated SA scenario	14
5.1 Steady-state analyses	14
5.2 SA1-D1-ATF results	14
6 iPWR Design-2: Summary of the results of the postulated SA scenario	20
6.1 Steady-state analyses	20
6.2 SA1-D2-ATF results	21
7 Conclusion	25
7.1 Evaluation of the performance of the codes	25
7.2 Lesson learned, best practise, and guidelines	26
References	27

1 Introduction

Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) are emerging as a flexible and innovative solution in the nuclear energy industry and they are designed to address the challenges of the current global energy demand. The development of SMRs is driven by the need for versatile and scalable power generation, improved safety through passive and inherent design features, cost-effective deployment, and suitability for industrial and off-grid applications [1]. A critical aspect of improving the safety of these designs is the development of accident-tolerant fuels (ATFs), or more currently Advanced Technology Fuels, which are tailored to maintain their overall integrity for longer in the event of a severe accident, thus extending the timeframe for an emergency response [2]. Among the most promising ATF candidates are Fe-based alloys such as FeCrAl, which offer superior oxidation resistance and mechanical properties compared to conventional Zr-based alloys [3, 4].

While SMRs, particularly the Integrated Pressurised Water Reactor (iPWR) concepts, incorporate features that boost safety and reinforce the first three levels of the Defence-in-Depth (DiD) principle, it is essential to systematically demonstrate their capability to prevent and manage Severe Accidents (SA). This includes providing independent prevention and mitigation features (DiD level 4) and supporting offsite emergency response (DiD level 5). Consequently, specific severe accident scenarios must be postulated and studied [5, 6].

Within this framework, the HORIZON-EURATOM 'Safety Analysis of SMRs with PAssive Mitigation Strategies for Severe Accidents' (SASPAM-SA) project was initiated in 2022. Coordinated by ENEA (Italy), the project involves 23 partners from 13 European countries and aims to investigate the applicability and transferability of knowledge from operating large-LWR reactors to iPWRs [7, 8, 9, 10, 11]. This research directly supports European licensing needs relating to SA and Emergency Planning Zone (EPZ) analyses, with the aim of establishing an independent European perspective on iPWR safety with regard to DiD levels 4 and 5 [5, 12]. As part of the SASPAM-SA project, a dedicated campaign was carried out in Work Package 2 (WP2-SCENARIOS), which focused on analyzing the impact of ATF cladding material on the SA progression of the selected generic reactor Designs 1 and 2. Design 1 of the iPWR is characterised by a submerged containment and an electric power output of ~60 MWe, while Design 2 of the iPWR, which has an electric power output of ~300 MWe, employs several passive systems and a dry containment. It is important to note that the project's goal is not to evaluate the designs, but rather to assess the capabilities of the integral codes used to simulate key phenomena occurring during the hypothetical scenarios postulated.

This report summarizes multiple studies on the safety analysis of the Design-1 and Design-2 in hypothetical SA scenarios with focus on the performance of ATF, in particular, of FeCrAl cladding material. Several partners conducted the analyses using different integral codes: Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Ruhr-University Bochum – Plant Simulation and Safety Group (RUB-PSS), Technical Research Center of Finland (VTT), Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development (ENEA), Lithuanian Energy Institute (LEI) and Sapienza University of Rome (UNIROMA1). The codes used during this evaluation were ASTEC, AC², and MELCOR. The primary objective was to evaluate the impact of FeCrAl cladding on accident progression, hydrogen generation and core degradation, compared with conventional Zircaloy cladding. This report provides a comparative analysis of the two iPWR designs and detailed descriptions of the modelling approaches for ATFs. It also presents comprehensive results from simulated severe accident scenarios and concludes with key lessons learned and recommendations for future research.

2 Generic iPWR Design-1 and Design-2 description

Both Design-1 and Design-2 are integral Pressurized Water Reactors (iPWRs), which integrate the reactor core, steam generators, and primary coolant pumps (in the case of Design-2) within a single Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV). This integral design philosophy enhances safety by eliminating large line breaks, which are a common cause of large break Loss-of-Coolant Accidents (LOCAs) in traditional PWRs. The geometric and operating specifications for both designs were defined in WP2 using publicly available sources and expert engineering judgment [13].

The generic Design 1 (see Figure 1) studied is a 160 MWth natural circulation iPWR. This integral design houses a shrouded core, a riser, a pressuriser and two helical tube steam generators (HTSGs) within the RPV. The entire unit is within a steel containment vessel that is submerged in a large pool of water, which serves as the ultimate heat sink. The significant thermal inertia provided by the large coolant inventory in the RPV, combined with the immersed containment, is enhanced by the near-vacuum atmosphere inside the containment, which promotes steam condensation in the event of steam release from the RPV. The reactor core comprises 37 fuel assemblies arranged in a 17×17 configuration, with an active height of around 2 meters [13]. This generic reactor concept incorporates two key passive safety systems, enhancing its accident scenarios management capabilities:

Emergency Core Cooling System (ECCS): It enhances heat removal by means of the Reactor Vent Valves (RVs), which are located at the top of the RPV. The steam discharged through these valves condenses on the interior surface of the containment and the resulting water is directed back to the core through the reactor recirculation valves (RRs), thus maintaining the core cooling even if multiple valves malfunction.

Containment Heat Removal System (CHRS): It dissipates heat through conduction and convection into a surrounding pool, providing an additional passive safety layer.

Figure 1: Representation of the generic iPWR Design-1 concept.

The generic Design-2 (see Figure 2) studied is characterised by the use of multiple passive systems, dry containment and a thermal power output of around 1000 MWe. It has an integral Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV) containing the core, steam generators (SG), control rod drive mechanism (CRDM), primary pumps and pressuriser (PRZ) [13]. It operates in forced circulation during normal operation conditions and adopts a passive mitigation strategy in the event of an accident as follows:

- **Natural Circulation in the RPV:** Following the primary pump trip, coolant flow is sustained by natural circulation. Additional low-level riser-downcomer connections ensure circulation at reduced coolant levels.
- **Decay Heat Removal:** It operates via natural circulation between steam generators and an elevated pool containing a submerged heat exchanger.
- **Primary Automatic Depressurization System (ADS):** This system is designed to automatically reduce RPV pressure, enabling the activation of passive safety injection systems.
- **High-Pressure Safety Injection:** Borated water is injected into the RPV from a dedicated tank that is connected at the top and bottom. When activated, a natural circulation loop is formed between the tank and the RPV.
- **Low-Pressure Safety Injection:** This system is driven solely by gravity and consists of elevated tanks that deliver coolant to the RPV via the direct vessel injection (DVI) line.
- **Containment Pressure Suppression:** To mitigate pressure buildup inside the containment area, steam is directed into a large pool of water via dedicated DryWell (DW) connections.
- **Flooding of the Reactor Cavity:** Under SA conditions, the reactor cavity is flooded automatically to cool the external surface of the RPV lower head and support in-vessel melt retention.

Figure 2: Representation of the generic iPWR Design-2 concept.

More information about Design 1 and 2 and the major hypothesis are report in [14, 15]

3 ATF Modelling Approaches

The development of advanced nuclear fuel cladding materials is a critical area of research, particularly in order to enhance safety margins during a SA. During a LOCA, the reactor core is exposed to high-temperature steam, which leads to several physical and chemical degradation phenomena [16, 17]. While current zirconium-based alloys are effective under normal operating conditions, they exhibit significant limitations in these off-normal conditions. They are susceptible to bursting at temperatures between 700 °C and 1100 °C due to high internal pressure, and they undergo fast, self-catalysed exothermic reactions with high-temperature steam. These reactions generate a large quantity of heat, which accelerates the temperature increase, and produce significant amounts of hydrogen gas, increasing the risk of hydrogen detonation and the release of radioactive fission products [3, 16, 17, 18]. Following the Fukushima nuclear accident, there was more attention on shifting the paradigm towards ATFs, which involve replacing zirconium alloys with materials that demonstrate significantly slower oxidation kinetics in high-temperature steam environments. This would enhance safety margins and reduce critical heat generation rates.

Among the different candidate materials for ATF cladding that have been investigated, iron-chromium-aluminium (FeCrAl) alloys have emerged as a particularly promising option [17]. These alloys have a successful proven history in industries requiring high-temperature oxidation resistance, including environments containing steam [16]. For nuclear applications, FeCrAl alloys offer several attractive properties, including good formability and high mechanical strength. Most notably, they exhibit significantly improved oxidation kinetics in high-temperature steam environments compared to zirconium-based alloys, demonstrating oxidation rates over two orders of magnitude lower than zirconium alloys at temperatures below 1400 °C. This superior oxidation resistance is attributed to the selective formation of a dense, adherent Al_2O_3 layer on the alloy surface at high temperatures [3, 16, 17]. Although there are challenges, such as higher thermal neutron absorption compared to zirconium, these can be mitigated by strategies such as reducing cladding thickness or increasing fuel enrichment. Ongoing optimisation efforts aim to balance the elemental composition, such as the chromium and aluminium content, in order to address potential issues like embrittlement whilst maintaining enhanced accident tolerance performance [3, 4, 16]. This has resulted in a number of FeCrAl candidates such as C26M2 and B136Y3 (see Table 1 for the alloys compositions). In particular, the alloy designated as B136Y3 has been extensively tested in separate-effects tests and in bundle test conditions at then QUENCH material testing facility at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany.

Studies conducted under isothermal conditions have demonstrated that a parabolic law governs the steam oxidation kinetics of FeCrAl [3]:

$$\frac{dm_o^2}{dt} = K_{Ox}$$

where m_o [kg/m^2] is the total oxygen mass gain, t [s] is the time and K_{Ox} [kg^2/m^4s] is the kinetics constant that follows an Arrhenius formulation:

$$K_{Ox} = Aexp(-Q/RT)$$

where T [K] is the cladding absolute temperature, $R = 8.31446$ [J/molK] is the ideal gas constant, A [kg^2/m^4s] is the pre-exponential constant and Q [J/mol] is the activation energy.

Additionally, these studies demonstrate the complexity of FeCrAl oxidation. A single Arrhenius pair (A, Q) is insufficient to represent oxidation behaviour across the full investigated temperature range (873 K to 1773 K). Below 1573 K, the dominant protective oxide is alumina, which can form as either α - or θ -alumina, depending on the temperature, with each form exhibiting different kinetic characteristics. In contrast, temperatures above 1673 K led to rapid and complete oxidation, with rates similar to those observed for pure iron. The Arrhenius parameters derived from experimental observations are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Arrhenius constants for FeCrAl oxidation kinetics, derived from experimental data [3].

Temperature Range	$A \left[\frac{kg^2}{m^4s} \right]$	$Q \left[\frac{J}{mol} \right]$	Comments
$873 \text{ K} \leq T < 1173 \text{ K}$	5.376×10^{-3}	1.847×10^5	θ -alumina kinetics
$1173 \text{ K} \leq T < 1273 \text{ K}$	4.692×10^{-12}	0.0	-
$1273 \text{ K} \leq T < 1648 \text{ K}$	5.018	2.877×10^5	α -alumina kinetics
$T \geq 1648 \text{ K}$	2.4×10^8	3.527×10^5	Fe-oxide kinetics

Table 2 shows the partners involved in Task 2.3 of WP2-SCENARIOS, the codes used, and the reactor designs to which they contributed. Although FeCrAl-related data was provided to all partners, each team had full autonomy to use their own input data and available model implementations. It should be noted that while high-temperature steam oxidation kinetics for FeCrAl was explicitly modelled, the current frameworks do not incorporate specific models for the thermomechanical degradation leading to cladding loss of integrity, such as ballooning, bursting, or FeCrAl relocation mechanisms.

Table 2. Partners and Codes used for the Task 2.3

Partner	Code	iPWR Concept
KIT	ASTEC	Design 1
RUB-PSS	AC ²	
VTT	MELCOR	
ENEA	ASTEC	Design 2
LEI	AC ²	
UNIROMA1	MELCOR	

3.1 ATF Modelling Approach for ASTEC

At the time of the study, ASTEC does not include a specific oxidation model for FeCrAl alloys that accounts for all complex phenomena¹. A practical solution was adopted by overwriting default properties of Zr-based alloys using the MDB structure in the Input-Deck level. This allows user-defined customization of material properties.

KIT – Design 1

Two approaches were considered while maintaining core geometry unchanged [19]:

- **KIT-ATF1:** The existing framework for Zr-based alloys was used, and only the steam oxidation correlation was replaced with the corresponding one for FeCrAl. The FeCrAl oxidation kinetics were based on a parabolic rate law, with temperature-dependent Arrhenius constants presented in Table 1. In this initial approach, the thermophysical, mechanical and thermodynamic properties of the Zircaloy cladding structure were not modified and all values remained at their default settings. The aim is to isolate and interpret the impact of replacing Zircaloy's oxidation kinetics with those of FeCrAl.

KIT-ATF2: In addition to modifying the oxidation correlation, main thermophysical and thermodynamical properties of FeCrAl (density, thermal conductivity, heat capacity, liquid viscosity, surface tension, melting temperature, enthalpy, among others) were included [4], replacing those of Zr and its oxides. This is built

¹ Currently, there are ongoing developments by Z. I. Jiménez et al. [25] aimed at proposing a dedicated modelling of FeCrAl oxidation in an upcoming ASTEC version. This work enhances existing capabilities by accounting for the loss of integrity of the protective alumina layer around 1600 K, which subsequently leads to accelerated iron oxidation at higher temperatures.

upon the ATF1 approach but does not account for thermomechanical properties or fuel/structural material interaction during degradation. Furthermore, in the simulations performed, the corium oxidation model (UZOXMAG) remained activated to account for oxidation after the loss of cladding geometry. This model was originally developed to simulate the state-dependent oxidation kinetics of Zirconium in the corium; as a result, once core degradation reaches an advanced stage, its use for FeCrAl introduces notable uncertainties in the predicted oxidation behaviour and the results must be interpreted with caution.

ENEA – Design 2

In the assessment carried out by ENEA, the geometry of the core remained unchanged with the FeCrAl implementation, as did the thermo-physical parameters of the cladding material, which were kept the same as in the reference calculation using traditional zirconium (Zr) cladding. The oxidation kinetic law of Zr was directly substituted with that of FeCrAl (Table 1) using the MDB structure of the code [20].

3.2 ATF Modelling Approach for AC²

ATF modelling has been included in AC² since version 2023.1. It is assumed that, due to the oxidation of FeCrAl, only a protective layer of α -Al₂O₃ is produced. The oxidation rate is based on a parabolic rate law similar to that for zirconium oxidation and is determined by an Arrhenius equation with a reduction factor for steam starvation. Generally, the code uses the material properties of the specified cladding type. If a material other than the standard Zircaloy is used, the corresponding values must be indicated by the user.

AC² offers three options for FeCrAl oxidation modelling:

Option 20: FeCrAl oxidation based on experiments with KANTHAL APM material (69wt% Fe, 21.6% Cr, 4.9%Al, 4.5% balance). Constants: $A = 3.1 [kg^2/m^4s]$ and $Q = 2.785 \times 10^5 [J/mol]$.

Option 21: Similar to the previous option, but with the constants multiplied by 300 [21, 22].

Option 22: This is a user-defined input that allows only a single temperature range to be defined.

RUB-PSS – Design 1

Option 21 of the FeCrAl modelling was used for the AC² code. Several of the model's parameters and the geometrical values of the fuel rods were adopted from open literature [21]. Some FeCrAl parameters were adopted or derived from Zircaloy or iron, as consistent and reliable data for FeCrAl alloys is not yet available.

LEI – Design 2

Option 20 of the FeCrAl modelling was used for the AC² code. The material properties (e.g., density, heat capacity and melting temperature) of the cladding were identical to those of the Zr cladding used in the current ATF case [22].

3.3 ATF Modelling Approach for MELCOR

In MELCOR, the generalized oxidation model uses an Arrhenius equation with user-defined constants (A and B, which are equivalent to A and Q/R in this report, respectively) to calculate the cladding oxidation kinetics constant for different temperature ranges.

VTT – Design 1

The physical properties of zirconium were replaced with the properties of FeCrAl, and the properties of ZrO₂ were replaced with 'FeCrAl oxide'. These properties were taken from the MELCOR Material Properties

Reference Manual. Experimental oxidation kinetics data from Kim et al. [3] were used to fit an Arrhenius equation to two temperature ranges for the kinetics constant:

- ≤ 1573 K: $A = 1.66 \times 10^{-2} [kg^2/m^4s]$ and $B = 22334 [K]$.
- ≥ 1673 K: $A = 2.48 \times 10^8 [kg^2/m^4s]$ and $B = 39282 [K]$.

The code performs an interpolation between the two temperature limits where the coefficients are not defined. A limitation of the current generalized oxidation model in MELCOR is that the oxidation enthalpy cannot be modified by a user, meaning the model uses the Zr oxidation enthalpy, which is greater than the FeCrAl oxidation enthalpy. This leads to an overestimation of the energy generated during breakaway oxidation (above 1573 K) and, consequently, an overestimation of the cladding temperature. It was assumed that the cladding was the same thickness as the Zr reference material [23].

UNIROMA1 – Design 2

Physical properties (melting point, density, specific heat, thermal conductivity and enthalpy) for both FeCrAl and FeCrAl oxide were taken from the literature and implemented in the Material Properties package. Oxidation reactions for Fe and Al were implemented (the Cr reaction was omitted due to its low impact), using parabolic rate constants from Kim et al. [3]. The eutectic model was deactivated due to consecutive code crashes. The cladding thickness was kept equal to the reference Zr to maintain the core geometry unchanged [24].

4 Postulated accident scenarios

To test the performance of the different codes when using ATF cladding material, a hypothetical scenario was postulated for each design. These scenarios involve significant postulated system failures leading to core uncover and heat-up, initiating oxidation processes. The main focus of the analysis is the production of hydrogen as a major safety risk and the potential delay to the progression of the accident in comparison with Zr cladding.

Two different assumptions were adopted regarding core conditions. Some partners used the End-of-Cycle (EOC) fuel inventory with a burnup of 60 MWd/tU, which was generated in Task 2.4 of WP2–SCENARIOS using CASMO5. Others applied a decay heat curve based on the ANS73 standard, adding a 20% of power.

4.1 Generic iPWR Design-1

A hypothetical SA sequence has been postulated for the generic iPWR Design-1, initiated by opening a break of the Chemical and Volume Control System (CVCS) discharge line with loss of AC power supply. The break, with a diameter of about ~0.004 m, is located above the top of active core, creating a pathway between the downcomer and the containment. To prevent reverse flow through the break, it is placed at an elevated position of ~5.6 m or ~6.5 above the top of active fuel (TAF), according to the modelling assumptions adopted by each participant. This scenario corresponds to the one designated as SA-1 in the Deliverable 2.2 [15] and it will be designated as SA1-D1-ATF in this report.

The SA sequence involves:

- Loss of AC power supply;
- Main Steam Line (MSL) closure with a delay of ~5 seconds;
- ECCS is activated when the pressure difference between the containment and the RPV falls below about 6.2 MPa or 6.9 MPa, depending on the partner, and the water level in the containment rises above ~ 5.8 m, slightly exceeding the position elevation of the RRs;
- RVs work normally, but both RRs are assumed not available in closed position.

4.2 Generic iPWR Design-2

The SA scenario selected to assess the ATF effects on the Design-2 correspond to the SA-1 from the Deliverable 2.2 [15]. The initiating event of this hypothetical sequence is a guillotine break of one Direct Vessel Injection (DVI) line and the unavailability of the EHRS system, while all other systems are operational. This scenario will be designated as SA-D2-ATF in this report. A summary of the control logic of the safety systems is listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Summary of set points and safety systems actuations considered in the SA1-D2-ATF of Design 2

Event	Actuation condition
Break of DVI line-A	t = 0 s
Safety-Signal	High Containment Pressure set-point: $P_{PRZ} > 1.7$ bar
SCRAM	Safety-Signal + about 5 s delay
Secondary system isolation	Safety-Signal + about 5 s delay
Turn-off of the primary pressure controls	Safety-Signal + about 5 s delay
EHRS actuation	FAILED
Low PRZ level signal	Low PRZ water level set-point: PRZ level < 14%
RCP Coastdown	Low PRZ level + about 15 s delay

Event	Actuation condition
RI-DC valves opening	Low PRZ level + about 16 s delay
Low PRZ pressure signal	Low PRZ pressure set-point: $P_{PRZ} < \text{about } 117.2 \text{ bar}$
EBTs opening	Low PRZ pressure + about 5 s delay
ADS stage-1 actuation	Low PRZ pressure + about 8 s delay
Low DP RPV-Containment signal	Low RPV - Containment differential pressure set-point: $P_{PRZ} - P_{DW} < \text{about } 0.5 \text{ bar}$
LGMS actuation	Low RPV – Containment signal + about 5 seconds delay
Low LGMS mass signal	Low LGMS mass set-point: Water volume in one of the two LGMS tanks < 8%
ADS stage-2 actuation	Low LGMS mass signal

5 iPWR Design-1: Summary of the results of the postulated SA scenario

The postulated SA scenario in the generic iPWR Design-1 has been analysed by means of ASTEC v3.1 (KIT), AC² (RUB-PSS), and MELCOR v2.2 (VTT).

5.1 Steady-state analyses

The results of the steady state analyses by the different codes are shown in Table 4. There were no significant changes to the initial conditions when comparing the Zr alloy and the FeCrAl cladding material, since most participants assumed that there was no change to the core geometry. However, some minor differences were observed for AC², which may be attributed to geometric changes when applying the FeCrAl alloy.

Table 4. iPWR Design-1: results of the steady state analyses.

Parameter	ASTEC ATF1 (KIT)	ASTEC ATF2 (KIT)	ASTEC Zr (KIT)	AC ² ATF (RUB- PSS)	AC ² Zr (RUB- PSS)	MELCOR ATF (VTT)	MELCOR Zr (VTT)
Core Power (MW)	160	160	160	160	160	160	160
PRZ Pressure (MPa)	12.70	12.70	12.70	12.81	12.78	12.76	12.76
PRZ Level (m)	1.975	1.975	1.975	2.2	2.2	1.97	1.97
T Inlet Core (K)	534.1	534.1	534.1	539	539	537	531
T Outlet Core (K)	586.2	586.2	586.2	592.8	592.8	588	583
Primary Mass Flow Rate (kg/s)	586.8	586.8	586.8	533.4	553.4	587	587
T Inlet SG (K)	421.9	421.9	421.9	421.9	421.9	422	422
P inlet SG (MPa)	3.57	3.57	3.57	3.5	3.5	3.49	3.49
T Outlet SG (K)	574.9	574.9	574.9	580.2	580.2	579	580
P outlet SG (MPa)	3.45	3.45	3.45	3.33	3.3	3.447	3.448
Steam Super heat degree (K)	59.9	59.9	59.9	67	67	64	65
Secondary Mass Flow Rate (kg/s)	68.7	68.7	68.7	67.1	67.1	67	67
Containment Pressure (Pa)	690	690	690	1780	-	600	600
Containment Water Level (m)	0	0	0	0	0	-	-
Containment Air Temperature (K)	320.0	320.0	320.0	366	366	419	419
External Pool water level (m)	16.78	16.78	16.78	15.67	15.7	16.76	16.76
External Pool liquid Temperature (K)	320.00	320.00	320.00	320	320	320	320

5.2 SA1-D1-ATF results

The postulated SA1-D1-ATF scenario is initiated by a break on the CVCS discharge line, followed by the loss of AC, SG feedwater, and the MSI valves isolation. The break discharges directly into the containment. To avoid the reverse flow of the liquid accumulating in the containment due to the break, and then following the activation of the ECCS, the partners decided on different strategies to locate the break. Specifically, KIT

located the break at about 5.6 m, RUB-PSS at about 6.5 m and VTT at about 3.5 m, all above the TAF. In the case of VTT, the discharge was set to a higher elevation (9 m from the bottom of the Cont.). In addition, each partner was free to select the decay heat model to be used in their simulations. KIT computed the decay heat using the ASTEC model, based on the fission product inventory provided in Task 2.4. RUB-PSS adopted the ANS-1973 standard with a 20% margin, whereas VTT used the standard's nominal correlation.

The summary of the results by the different partners using FeCrAl and Zircaloy as cladding material are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. iPWR Design 1: Progression of the postulated SA1-D1-ATF and SA-1 (Zr) scenarios

Key events/parameters	ASTEC ATF1 (KIT)	ASTEC ATF2 (KIT)	ASTEC Zr (KIT)	AC ² ATF (RUB)	AC ² Zr (RUB)	MELCOR (VTT)	MELCOR (VTT)
Scram time (s)	4.3	4.3	4.3	0	0	4	4
ECCS signal (s)	934.8	937.8	934.1	4177	4537	513	512
Max. water level in Cont. (m)	9.76	9.65	9.75	8.28	8.56	8.35	8.32
Max. pressure in Cont. (MPa)	2.65	2.65	2.65	4.94	4.83	4.68	4.67
Core TAF uncovered (s)	3817	3833	3851	5493	6130	3960	4050
Core BAF uncovered (s)	23000	22382	22483	11519	15254	10290	10920
H ₂ on-set (s)	7518.8	7593.8	7534.7	8117	7482	7860	7500
Total H ₂ produced in the vessel (kg)	48.9	28.1	64.0	10.95	73.0	69.0	90.0
Total H ₂ produced by cladding oxidation (kg)	27.1	11.7	28.7	-	-	-	-
Final H ₂ mass in Cont. (kg)	41.2	24.6	53.95	-	-	48.0	62.0
First slump of corium with FPs in the LP (s)	29350	30460	29515	15521	11050	25245	23671
Mass of corium relocated in the LP (kg)	7627.8	9018.1	5770.8	6584.8	8459.5	3112	2967
RPV failure (s)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

As can be observed in Table 5, although there are discrepancies in the activation time of the ECCS signal between the codes, mainly due to the elevation at which each partner located the break, there are no significant differences in the implementation of the ATF material for both ASTEC and MELCOR. In the case of AC², activation is observed to occur approximately 360 seconds earlier, which could be explained by geometric modifications introduced when applying the ATF model. Similarly, other variables, such as the maximum water level and containment pressure, did not show significant changes. Since the RRs are assumed to remain closed in the proposed scenario, no water re-entry to the core from the containment is possible. As a result, the core becomes fully uncovered after approximately 22400 seconds for ASTEC, 11500 seconds for AC², and 10300 seconds for MELCOR. The times at which the water level reaches the TAF and BAF also remain essentially unchanged for ASTEC and MELCOR when using ATF. For AC², however, an earlier occurrence is noted, with the water level reaching TAF and BAF approximately 640 and 3730 seconds earlier, respectively. The differences between the codes were discussed in detail in Deliverable 2.2 [15].

Figure 3. Postulated SA1-D1-ATF: Pressure evolution in the RPV and in the Containment.

Figure 4. Postulated SA1-D1-ATF: Pressure evolution in the RPV and in the Containment for Zircaloy and FeCrAl cladding by the partners – KIT, RUB-PSS, VTT.

Figure 3 shows the pressure evolution in both the containment and the RPV for ASTEC [19], AC² [21] and MELCOR [23] using FeCrAl cladding during the initial phase of the accident sequence. Overall, a similar behaviour can be observed across the simulations: following the break initiation there is a depressurization of the RPV and a pressure increase in the containment until the ECCS activation conditions are met. This action results in a pressure equalization between both domains, followed by a gradual pressure decrease until a quasi-steady-state value is reached. A peak increase in pressure associated with corium relocation in the lower plenum is observed at approximately 30,000 seconds for ASTEC and 25,000 seconds for MELCOR. This effect is not evident in the pressure evolution results obtained with AC².

Figure 4 shows a comparison of pressure evolution in the containment and the RPV for each code, considering both FeCrAl and Zircaloy cladding. In general, no significant differences are observed. However, for ASTEC and MELCOR, a small delay in corium relocation to the lower plenum is observed when FeCrAl is used. For all codes, the pressure in the containment is slightly lower when FeCrAl is used than when Zircaloy is used. This is primarily due to the reduced hydrogen production of FeCrAl, resulting in a lower hydrogen content in the containment than in the reference cases.

Figure 5. Postulated SA1-D1-ATF: Peak cladding temperature behaviour during the initial phase of the SA sequence.

The loss of coolant and the subsequent inability to keep cooling the core (RRs closed) result in an increase in core temperature. Figure 5 shows the peak cladding temperature evolution during the initial phase of the accident sequence for the codes used. As can be seen, the temperature begins to increase slowly for all cases between 5000 and 6000 seconds. However, a clear difference is shown for the fast temperature escalation as the temperature increases. In ASTEC, implementing ATF materials causes a delay in the onset of rapid temperature escalation of around 1730 seconds when using ATF1 (pink dashed line — only the new oxidation correlation applied) and 2130 seconds with ATF2 (solid red line — correlation and thermophysical property modifications). Similarly, in MELCOR, a delay of around 1250 seconds in temperature escalation is observed when ATF is implemented. In contrast, no rapid temperature escalation is observed in AC²; instead, the temperature increases linearly, although it reaches higher values than in the Zr-based case between 6000 and 10000 seconds after accident initiation. These differences can be attributed to the modelling and

implementation approaches used for FeCrAl as an ATF cladding material, such as in the case of AC², where no transition in oxidation kinetics at 1648 K was considered, unlike in the other cases.

The most significant difference observed for each code relates to the total amount of hydrogen produced in the vessel during the core degradation. Figure 6 shows the total amount of hydrogen produced in the core during the first 30000 seconds of the accident, comparing the results obtained using FeCrAl and Zircaloy cladding. Generally, a significant reduction in hydrogen production is observed when FeCrAl is used, especially in the early stages of core degradation. It is important to note that the total hydrogen displayed comes from not only cladding oxidation, but also corium and structural material oxidation. As shown in Table 5 for ASTEC simulations, cladding oxidation accounts for around 45% of the total hydrogen produced in the vessel. Regarding the post-relocation phase, it should be noted that the corium oxidation model (e.g. UZOXMAG in ASTEC) was activated. This model applies zirconium-based oxidation kinetics to the molten corium, which introduces uncertainty to the results, as it does not account for iron-chromium-aluminium-specific interactions within the melt. In a similar manner to the temperature evolution, the onset of rapid hydrogen generation is delayed when FeCrAl is used: by approximately 0.6 hours in ASTEC and 0.35 hours in MELCOR. By contrast, no rapid hydrogen escalation is observed in AC² with the FeCrAl approach implemented.

Figure 6. Postulated SA1-D1-ATF: Total hydrogen generation during the initial phase of the SA sequence.

Figure 7. Postulated SA1-D1-ATF: Total hydrogen generation (left) at the end of the calculated scenario, (right) before reaching a peak cladding temperature of 1648 (K).

Once the cladding temperature exceeds 1648 (K) and approaches the material’s melting point, complex interactions with the other core materials may occur, resulting in significant uncertainty in the displayed values. This is primarily because either there are currently no refined models capable of accurately capturing such interactions when FeCrAl material is used or there are limitations in the available correlations and estimations. Therefore, Figure 7 displays two plots. The plot on the left shows the cumulative hydrogen generation at the end of the simulations, while the plot on the right presents the total hydrogen generated before the cladding peak temperature reaches 1648 (K) for FeCrAl and Zr. Implementing the ATF2 approach in ASTEC resulted in a 56% reduction for the final amount of H₂. In AC², applying the ATF model led to an 85% reduction, whereas in MELCOR, the reduction was only 23%. Significantly higher reductions in hydrogen generation are observed when considering the amount generated up to the point when the cladding reaches 1648 K: approximately 71% for ASTEC-ATF2 (64% for ASTEC-ATF1), 90% for AC² and 95% for MELCOR. These differences are primarily due to the different ATF implementation strategies adopted by each partner, as discussed in Section 3. These reductions are physically consistent with the superior oxidation resistance of FeCrAl, which has kinetics that are orders of magnitude lower than those of Zircaloy as long as the protective alumina layer remains intact. However, behaviour beyond this point is driven by the activation of rapid iron oxidation once the protective scale has failed. It is important to note that, at 1648 K, the cladding retains its rod-like geometry. However, subsequent degradation differs from that of Zircaloy due to FeCrAl’s different melting point. This difference changes the timing and kinetics of material relocation into the melt, significantly impacting the late-phase figures of merit (e.g. hydrogen generation). This effect is further compounded by the activation of the corium oxidation model (UZOXMAG for ASTEC) on the relocated mass. An important aspect is that none of the simulated cases resulted in vessel failure. This is similar to the reference cases that used Zircaloy as cladding material.

6 iPWR Design-2: Summary of the results of the postulated SA scenario

The postulated SA scenario in the generic iPWR Design-2 has been analysed by means of ASTEC v3.1 (ENEA), AC² (LEI), and MELCOR v2.2 (UNIROMA1).

All the partners employed the decay heat power computed in the framework of the WP2 – Task 2.4.

6.1 Steady-state analyses

The results of the steady state analyses by the simulation codes used (ASTEC, AC² and MELCOR) are shown in Table 6. The key parameters analyzed showed good agreement between the ATF simulation and their Zr-based reference values across these simulations, with very small deviations observed. However, certain deviations were noted for c parameters. In particular, the pressurizer level in AC² (not shown in Table 6 but available in [22]) was intentionally lowered from its reference value to align with specific control logic, ensuring that the recirculation pumps tripped before the ADS-1 system activated. Despite these minor adjustments and differences in parameters such as secondary mass flow rates (particularly in AC²), these were considered to have a limited impact on subsequent accident transients since the secondary circuit becomes isolated at the beginning of the accident. Overall, these steady-state calculations successfully provided a consistent and representative baseline for the detailed severe accident analyses.

Table 6. iPWR Design-2: results of the steady state analyses

Parameter	ASTEC ATF (ENEA)	ASTEC Zr (ENEA)	AC2 ATF (LEI)	AC2 Zr (LEI) ²	MELCOR ATF (UNIROMA1)	MELCOR Zr (UNIROMA1) ³
Core Power (MW)	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000
PRZ Pressure (MPa)	15.5	15.5	15.52	15.6	15.5	15.2
T Inlet Core (K)	571.2	571.2	566.1	565.1	571.1	569.7
T Outlet Core (K)	607.1	607.1	602.3	602.4	605.5	605.6
Primary Mass Flow Rate (kg/s)	4714	4714	4697.5	4699.7	4697.9	4654.8
T Inlet SG (K)	497.0	497.0	497.2	496.0	497.1	497.0
P Inlet SG (MPa)	6.11	6.1	6.23	5.8	6.2	6.2
T Outlet SG (K)	592.1	592.1	586.5	569.0	591.3	593.4
P Outlet SG (MPa)	5.80	5.80	5.95	5.8	5.92	5.9
Steam Super Heat Degree (K)	45.2	45.2	42.1	21.0	46.5	45.7
Secondary Mass Flow Rate (kg/s)	512.9	512.9	542.5	520.0	501.7	500.5
Containment Pressure (MPa)	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1016	0.1
Containment Water Level (m)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Containment Air Temperature (K)	323.2	323.2	321.4	324.0	319.7	320.2
External Pool Water Level (m)	9.0	9.0	9.0	10.0	9.0	9.0
External Pool Water Temperature (K)	293.15	293.15	322.05	-	293.01	293.15

² Data taken from Deliverable 2.2 [15]

³ Data taken from Deliverable 2.2 [15]

6.2 SA1-D2-ATF results

The postulated SA1-D2-ATF scenario is initiated by a guillotine break of one Direct Vessel Injection (DVI) line at time zero, which represents a Small Break Loss of Coolant Accident (SB-LOCA). A critical assumption of this scenario is the unavailability of the EHRS system, while all other systems are kept operational.

Following the break, the main early safety actions are initiated, with no significant differences observed between simulations using either FeCrAl or Zircaloy. SCRAM and secondary system isolation occur within 25 to 45 (s). The primary coolant pumps (RCPs) coast down and the RI-DC valves open in response to a signal indicating a low PRZ level, typically between 105 and 162 (s). Finally, the EBTs and ADS-1 systems are activated when the PRZ pressure falls below the activation setpoint, which is generally between 172 and 311 seconds.

The summary of the results by the different partners using FeCrAl and Zircaloy as cladding material are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. iPWR Design-2: Progression of the postulated SA1-D2-ATF and SA-1 (Zr) scenarios

Phenomenon	ASTEC ATF (ENEA)	ASTEC Zr (ENEA)	AC2 ATF (LEI)	AC2 Zr (LEI)	MELCOR ATF (UNIROMA1)	MELCOR Zr (UNIROMA1)
Start of the transient: DVI break (s)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Scram time (s)	25	25	45	45	27	27
Actuation of the EHRS (s) ⁴	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
RCP Coast-down (s)	105	105	162	162	157	157
RI-DC valves opening (s)	106	106	162	162	157	157
Actuation of EBT (s)	311	311	227	227	173	172
Containment Design Pressure Reached (s) ⁵	800	800	801	801	670	670
Core TAF uncovered (s)	5829	5830	5257	5360	1715	3133
H ₂ on-set (s)	18150	11500	9799	6998	18550	18550
Start of FPs release from fuel (s)	12589	12528	-	-	-	-
Cladding Temperature reached 1648 K (s)	-	-	12049	11598	33668	24878
Actuation of LGMS (s)	21884	18586	10267	10267	11320	10350
Core BAF uncovered (s)	-	-			100478	111511
Time first corium slump (s)	-	-			113400	63000
Time second corium slump (s)					-	118240

The SB-LOCA coupled with ADS-1 activation and EHRS failure leads to rapid pressurisation of the containment. The containment design pressure is reached relatively early in the transient, at around 670–800 seconds. The failure of the containment is assumed for ASTEC and MELCOR models, while AC² considers a venting valve that opens and closes based on threshold values. During this period, water begins to fill the reactor cavity.

⁴ N/A: Not Available

⁵ The containment design pressure was set at 1.45 MPa for ASTEC model (ENEA) [20] and at 1.2 MPa for the MELCOR model (UNIROMA1) [24]. In the AC² model (LEI) [22], an unfiltered venting valve was set to open at 0.9 MPa and close at 0.8 MPa to manage the increase in pressure in the containment.

As the RPV depressurises, the water level gradually decreases and the core becomes uncovered. The core level reaches the TAF after approximately 1715 to 5830 (s), which initiates core degradation and then the onset of hydrogen production due to cladding oxidation. Although no significant differences were observed between the FeCrAl and Zr cases in terms of the time taken to reach TAF in ASTEC and AC², MELCOR simulations indicated that for the FeCrAl case, the core level would reach the TAF approximately 24 minutes earlier.

Figure 8. Postulated SA1-D2-ATF: Normalized collapsed level evolution during the initial phase of the SA sequence

Figure 9. Postulated SA1-D2-ATF: Peak cladding temperature behaviour during the initial phase of the SA sequence.

Figure 8 shows how the core water level evolves when using the different codes for FeCrAl and a comparison with the results obtained using Zircaloy. The ATF material implementation delays the point at which the core level reaches the bottom of the active fuel (BAF). For ASTEC, this delay is approximately 1.5 hours, for AC², it is around 4.3 hours, and for MELCOR, it is about 3 hours. The BAF is reached at approximately 60000 seconds in MELCOR case.

Figure 9 displays the peak cladding temperature evolution simulated by the participating codes. A notable difference is observed in the timing of rapid temperature escalation depending on the cladding material. Specifically, ASTEC simulations show that ATF materials introduce a significant delay of approximately 5150 (s) (1.43 hours) before the onset of a rapid temperature increase. In contrast, AC² does not show a significant delay in escalation; however, FeCrAl cladding consistently presents lower temperatures compared to Zircaloy, even at elevated values. For MELCOR, while the Zircaloy case shows a rapid temperature escalation starting around 24500 seconds (6.8 h), the FeCrAl case presents a linear temperature progression without sudden increases.

Figure 10. Postulated SA1-D2-ATF: Total hydrogen generation during the first 50000 s of accident sequence.

The total in-vessel hydrogen generation calculated by the participating codes using FeCrAl cladding is presented in Figure 10, along a comparison with reference cases using Zircaloy cladding. Significant delays in the onset of hydrogen production and notable reductions in the total hydrogen mass generated were consistently reported by ENEA [20], LEI [22] and UNIROMA1 [24] during the simulations incorporating FeCrAl as the cladding material. These effects were more relevant during the early to intermediate phases of the accident sequence, highlighting the potential of an ATF material to delay hydrogen-related risks compared to conventional Zircaloy-based cladding. In the ASTEC simulation, hydrogen generation began at around 11500 (s) in the Zircaloy case, while the FeCrAl case showed a delayed onset of about 6650 (s) (1.85 hours). However, the H₂ generation becomes rather steep, due to the oxidation transition from aluminium oxide to iron oxide and corium oxidation, which may challenge the hydrogen-related risk. Similarly, MELCOR simulations showed hydrogen production starting at ~7000 (s) with Zircaloy and at ~9800 (s) with FeCrAl.

However, the AC² simulation showed no delay in the onset of hydrogen production, with generation starting at around 18550 (s) in both the reference and ATF cases.

As discussed previously for iPWR Design 1, significant uncertainties arise in predicting the behaviour of ATF materials interacting with other core components once core degradation progresses considerably. To show the effects of the cladding materials in the early stages of degradation, two plots are presented in

Figure 11. The plot on the left shows the mass of hydrogen generated in the vessel for both the Zircaloy and the FeCrAl cases at the point at which the peak cladding temperature reaches 1648 (K), which is identified as the transition temperature at which there is a change in the oxidation kinetics of the FeCrAl. The right-hand plot displays the delay time associated with reaching 1648 (K) for each cladding type. For both ASTEC and AC², the reduction in hydrogen production up to the transition temperature is greater than 95%, while in the case of MELCOR, it is only ~17%. However, the delay time for AC² to reach this transition temperature is only 0.13 hours for the ATF, whereas ASTEC and MELCOR take 1.34 and 2.44 hours, respectively. As mentioned previously, the difference in the hydrogen generation before 1648 K and the time delay arises from the superior resistance of FeCrAl when the alumina scale is intact. Once the scale fails, the rapid iron oxidation takes over. The differences between the codes can be attributed to the different approaches taking during the FeCrAl implementation.

Figure 11. Postulated SA1-D2-ATF: *left*) Total hydrogen generation before reaching a peak cladding temperature of 1648 (K), *right*) time delay to reach 1648 (K) by using FeCrAl cladding.

7 Conclusion

As part of Task 2.3 of Work Package 2 (WP2), the project partners conducted SA analyses of iPWR Design-1 and Design-2. The aim of these studies was to evaluate the impact of using ATF cladding made of FeCrAl instead of conventional Zirconium-based alloys. Different integral codes, including ASTEC, MELCOR and AC², were used to simulate hypothetical accident sequences and quantify the influence of FeCrAl on safety-critical phenomena such as hydrogen generation and onset time delays for temperature escalation.

7.1 Evaluation of the performance of the codes

The ASTEC, AC² and MELCOR codes demonstrated an overall ability to simulate severe accident scenarios while incorporating simplified models of ATF cladding. All three tools could capture the initial and intermediate phases of accident progression and reflect the key differences introduced by using FeCrAl instead of conventional zirconium-based cladding.

No major differences were observed across all partners when replacing Zircaloy with FeCrAl in the simulation of key thermal-hydraulic variables, such as primary and containment pressures, core water level and the timing of safety system activations, aside from minor discrepancies due to modelling assumptions such as break elevation or nodalization. However, the most significant variations between FeCrAl and Zr-based cladding cases were in oxidation-driven phenomena, including hydrogen generation, temperature escalation and the timing of core degradation, in particular for the early phase of the degradation.

The ability of each code to handle FeCrAl depended on the modelling approach used and the specific version of the code. Current ATF modelling approaches implemented in integral codes mainly involve substituting Zircaloy oxidation kinetics, and sometimes thermophysical properties, with those of FeCrAl:

- ASTEC: a simplified FeCrAl model was used, with only the oxidation kinetics replaced in the Zr structure of the code. KIT proposed a second approach, ATF2, that included property updates and showed greater hydrogen reduction and an increase of the delayed temperature rise. The lack of a dedicated model for FeCrAl degradation and relocation introduces uncertainty into the highly core degradation phase.
- AC²: the code allows user-defined oxidation kinetics to be used in addition to predefined aluminium oxidation models. However, it does not support rate-dependent kinetics, which can result in hydrogen production being underestimated in certain temperature ranges.
- MELCOR: the FeCrAl model is based on adjustments to oxidation kinetics and thermal properties. The early-phase results were satisfactory. However, VTT declared that the oxidation enthalpy remained fixed with a value taken for Zr, which could potentially lead to an overestimation of oxidation at high temperatures.

The thermomechanical response of FeCrAl, its detailed interactions with UO₂ fuel, and the relocation mechanisms of corium specific to FeCrAl have not yet been modelled adequately. This introduces significant uncertainties, particularly after the loss of cladding integrity in the late phases of core degradation. Although the simplifications carried out do not fully represent the complex behaviour of FeCrAl in advanced stages of core degradation, they are useful for initial assessments and for highlighting the potential advantages of ATF cladding.

7.2 Lesson learned, best practise, and guidelines

Improving the performance of ATF simulations, particularly for FeCrAl, requires making full use of the flexibility offered by simulation tools to allow material properties to be customised. Accurate modelling involves replacing the oxidation kinetics and adjusting key material parameters to reflect the unique characteristics of FeCrAl.

In the context of the analysed iPWR designs, FeCrAl cladding behaves as an accident-delaying material: while it does not entirely prevent core damage, in some cases it significantly delays the progression of severe accidents. One of the most significant advantages is the considerable decrease in hydrogen generation, attributed to the excellent oxidation resistance of FeCrAl during the early phase of the degradation and while the cladding keeps its rod-like geometry. This reduction plays a critical role in safety concerns related to hydrogen risk during severe accident scenarios.

Although initial steps have been taken to implement FeCrAl options in simulation codes, a major source of uncertainty in the late stages of severe accident progression is the lack of validated models of corium formation and relocation involving FeCrAl cladding. Addressing this gap requires the development of improved, experimentally dedicated models that represent the unique response of FeCrAl during advanced core degradation.

References

- [1] IAEA, "Design Safety Considerations for Water Cooled Small Modular Reactors Incorporating Lessons Learned from the Fukushima Daiichi Accident," IAEA-TECDOC-1785, Vienna, 2016.
- [2] IAEA, "Analysis of Options and Experimental Examination of Fuels for Water Cooled Reactors with Increased Accident Tolerance (ACTOF)," IAEA-TECDOC-1921, Vienna, 2020.
- [3] C. Kim, C. Tang, M. Große, Y. Maeng, C. Jang and M. Steinbrück, "Oxidation mechanism and kinetics of nuclear-grade FeCrAl alloys in the temperature range of 500-1500 °C in steam," *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, vol. 564, p. 153696, 2022.
- [4] P. Aragón, F. Feria and L. E. Herranz, "Modelling FeCrAl cladding thermo-mechanical performance. Part I: Steady-state conditions," *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, vol. 153, p. 104417, 2022.
- [5] IAEA, "Assessment of Defence in Depth for Nuclear Power Plants," Safety Reports Series No. 46, Vienna, Austria, 2005.
- [6] IAEA, "SMR Regulators' Forum Pilot Project Report: Considering the Application of a Graded Approach, Defence-in-Depth and Emergency Planning Zone Size for Small Modular Reactors," Vienna, Austria, 2018.
- [7] SASPAM-SA, "Safety Analysis of SMR with PAssive Mitigation strategies Severe Accident," 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.saspam-sa.eu>.
- [8] F. Mascari and e. al., "HORIZON EURATOM SASPAM-SA PROJECT: MAIN IDEAS AND FIRST OUTCOMES," in *International Conference on Small Modular Reactors and their Applications*, Vienna, Austria, 2024.
- [9] L. E. Herranz, B. Poubeau, L. Chailan and F. Mascari, "Looking ahead to severe accident research," *EPJ - Nuclear Sciences & Technologies*, vol. 11, 2025.
- [10] "Zenodo: Horizon Euratom Safety Analysis of SMR with PAssive Mitigation strategies - Severe Accident (SASPAM-SA) community;," [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/communities/saspam-sa/about>.
- [11] E. Commission, "CORDIS - EU Research Results: Safety Analysis of SMR with PAssive Mitigation strategies – Severe Accident (SASPAM-SA),," [Online]. Available: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059853>.
- [12] EC, "Safety Analysis of SMR with PAssive Mitigation strategies - Severe Accident (SASPAM-SA)," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059853>.
- [13] SASPAM-SA, "Milestone 2.1: Generic Data on Design 1 and Design 2," 2023.
- [14] Gabrielli and F., "Deliverable 2.1: Fuel inventory of the iPWR Design-1 and Design-2," <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14052163>, 2024.
- [15] F. Gabrielli, "Deliverable 2.2 - iPWR input-deck and scenarios analyses," SASPAM-SA, 2024.
- [16] Y. Yamamoto, B. Pint, K. Terrani, K. Field, Y. Yang and L. Snead, "Development and property evaluation of nuclear grade wrought FeCrAl fuel cladding for light water reactors," *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, no. 467, pp. 703-716, 2015.

- [17] C. Tang, A. Jianu, M. Steinbrueck, M. W. A. Grosse and H. J. Seifert, "Influence of composition and heating schedules on compatibility of FeCrAl alloys with high-temperature steam," *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, no. 511, pp. 496-507, 2018.
- [18] P. Aragon and F. F. H. L. Fera, "Modelling FeCrAl cladding thermo-mechanical performance. Part II: Comparative analysis with Zircaloy under LOCA conditions," *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, no. 163, 2023.
- [19] M. E. Cazado and F. Gabrielli, "Contribution of the KIT to the Task 2.3 activities: Annexes for Deliverable 2.3," SASPAM-SA, 2024.
- [20] P. Maccari, "Contribution of ENEA to the Task 2.3 activities - Annexes for Deliverable 2.3," SASPAM-SA, 2024.
- [21] J. Krieger, G. T. Stahlberg and M. K. Koch, "Contribution of RUB PSS to the WP2 - Task 2.3 activities: Annexes for Deliverable 2.3," SASPAM-SA, 2024.
- [22] M. Valincius and A. Kaliatka, "Contribution of the LEI to the Task 2.3 activities: Annexes for Deliverable 2.3," SASPAM-SA, 2024.
- [23] T. Sevón, "Contribution of VTT to the Task 2.3 activities: Annexes for Deliverable 2.3," SASPAM-SA, 2024.
- [24] M. Principato, "Contribution of UNIROMA1 to the Task 2.3 activities: Annexes for Deliverable 2.3," SASPAM-SA, 2024.
- [25] Z. I. Jiménez, F. Gabrielli, M. E. Cazado, V. H. Sánchez-Espniza, L. Laborde, L. Carenini and P. Draï, "ASTEC FeCrAl Model Validation and Application," in *12th ASTEC Users' Club Meeting*, Fontenay-aux-Roses, 2025.